

Depression in the elderly

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Abstract

Ageing of the world's population poses new challenges regarding care of individuals whose health undergoes a continuous process of physiological slow or accelerated degradation. However, these challenges do not only result from individual physiological processes but also from changes that occur in the entire population.

Keywords: ageing of the population, depression, advanced age

Introduction

According to estimates of the World Health Report, in 2025 the world population will reach over 800 million people above the age of 65, two thirds of them in developed countries. Therefore, ageing should be considered a global issue. The issue predominantly concerns European countries and is becoming increasingly visible in Poland [1].

There is an evident need for system and consistent solutions to problems of people whose ageing as well as loss of mental and physical capacities are becoming one of the major barriers in everyday, dignified life [1].

Development

Having reached the advanced age, people start a new stage in which they assess their whole life and the findings are not always positive. The issues of loneliness, uselessness, physical deficits, dependence of others or rejection emerge. The above together with common negative attitudes to the elderly can lead to withdrawal from activities and depressive disorders [2].

Mental disorders of old age are common and their aetiology differs. They include [3,4,5]:

- mental diseases earlier diagnosed (e.g. depression, bipolar affective disorder, schizophrenia)
- disorders associated with systemic and neurological diseases or CNS changes resulting from ageing
- dementia (e.g. Alzheimer's disease, angiogenic dementia)

- disturbances caused by external factors (e.g. loneliness, isolation).

During ageing various changes occur, including impaired protective processes, muscle atrophy or impaired efficiency of systems , i.e. the cardiovascular, respiratory and urinary ones. Moreover, the following are observed: reduced organ mass, bony structure losses, impaired sensory functioning, structural and anatomical changes of the ageing brain, i.e. increased ventricular volume and thinning of meninges [3].

Individuals > 65 years of age are considered the elderly. Older people are particularly exposed to risk factors of affective disorders, predominantly depression. Social loneliness, death of the spouse, loss of social roles, lower economic status, long-term and chronic diseases as well as their treatment favour the development of affective disorders, the depressive syndrome, in particular [3,5].

Conclusion

Depression in the elderly is a special diagnosis-, treatment- and care-related challenge for the entire therapeutic team. The role of those involved is to assist the elderly in organising their life, orient their interests and encourage them to be active. Moreover, it is crucial to establish the causes, diagnosis and differential diagnosis of depression in the elderly, to assess the clinical picture of disease, treatment options and professional nursing care [2].

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Conflict of interest:

The author have declared no conflict of interest.